

1 **Influence of Drying Temperature on the Quality Attributes and Bioactive Retention of**
2 ***Syzygium cumini* (Jamun) Pulp Powder**

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40 Graphical Abstract

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43 Jamun pulp was mechanically dehydrated and milled into fine powder. The standardized powder showed
44 significantly higher phenolics, ascorbic acid, and antioxidant activity than commercial fruit juice powders.
45 These findings indicate that dehydration at 55°C yields a bioactive-rich Jamun powder suitable for functional
46 food and nutraceutical applications.

47

48 Abstract

49 The present study was conducted to develop Jamun (*Syzygium cumini* L.) pulp powder with the
50 objective of preserving its bioactive phytochemicals and nutritional quality. Jamun pulp was
51 dehydrated using controlled mechanical drying at four different temperatures (45°C , 50°C , 55°C ,
52 and 60°C), followed by pulverization into fine powder. Among the tested conditions, drying at
53 55°C was identified as the optimum temperature, yielding the highest drying efficiency (12.43%)
54 and retaining the maximum total anthocyanin content (998.32 mg/100 g). The standardized
55 mechanically dried Jamun pulp powder exhibited significantly higher levels of total phenolics,
56 ascorbic acid, and antioxidant activity compared to commercially available fruit juice powders.
57 Additionally, the powder maintained a low moisture content, which enhanced its shelf stability
58 without compromising its physicochemical properties. The effective preservation of bioactive
59 constituents under controlled drying conditions highlights the importance of optimized processing
60 in minimizing nutrient degradation. Overall, the findings demonstrate that mechanical dehydration
61 at 55°C is an efficient method for producing bioactive-rich Jamun pulp powder, which can serve
62 as a natural antioxidant source and a promising functional ingredient for health-oriented food
63 formulations and nutraceutical applications.

64 **Keywords:** Jamun Pulp, Drying, Powder, Anthocyanins, Scanning Electron Microscopy, FTIR

65 1. Introduction

66 *Syzygium cumini* (L.) Skeels, commonly known as jamun or black plum, is a tropical fruit valued
67 for its rich content of bioactive compounds, particularly anthocyanins, phenolics, flavonoids, and
68 vitamin C that contribute to its vigorous free radical scavenging activity and functional food
69 potential (Shavronskaya et al., 2023). These natural compounds are known for their potent
70 antioxidant, antidiabetic, and anti-inflammatory properties, making jamun an excellent candidate
71 for developing functional foods and nutraceutical ingredients. However, the fruit is highly
72 perishable due to its high moisture content and soft texture, which limits its availability and market
73 potential in fresh form (Feng et al., 2023). The fruit has a deep purple to black colour due to the
74 presence of anthocyanin pigments, which are known for their antioxidant and health-promoting
75 effects (Kaur, 2024).

76 Despite its high nutritional value, the post-harvest utilization of jamun is limited because the fruit
77 is highly perishable, has a short harvesting season, and undergoes rapid spoilage after picking.
78 Therefore, to increase its shelf life and ensure year-round availability, processing techniques such
79 as drying can be effectively employed (Kanaujia et al., 2025). Drying is a traditional and widely
80 used preservation method that reduces the moisture content of the product, thereby preventing
81 microbial growth and enzymatic spoilage. Drying is one of the most effective methods to extend
82 the shelf life of jamun by reducing its moisture content and inhibiting microbial spoilage (Giri et
83 al., 2025). Converting jamun pulp into a powder form not only enhances its stability but also
84 provides a convenient ingredient for use in various food formulations, such as beverages, yoghurts,
85 bakery products, and ice creams (Ratti et al., 2024). Among the various factors influencing the
86 drying process, temperature plays a crucial role in determining the quality attributes (such as
87 colour, texture, solubility, and rehydration ability) as well as the retention of bioactive compounds
88 (Yikilkan et al., 2025). While higher drying temperatures can shorten the drying time and improve
89 process efficiency, they may also cause thermal degradation of heat-sensitive nutrients, such as
90 anthocyanins and vitamin C. Conversely, lower temperatures help preserve bioactive compounds
91 but may lead to longer drying times, higher energy costs, and potential microbial risks (Yin et al.,
92 2025). Converting jamun pulp into powder form through drying enhances storage stability, reduces
93 packaging and transportation costs, and provides a convenient ingredient for use in various food
94 formulations such as smoothies, candies, yoghurts, bakery products, and health supplements
95 (Rafiquzzaman et al., 2025).

96 Moreover, jamun powder can serve as a natural colorant and functional additive due to its
97 anthocyanin content. However, the drying temperature has a significant influence on the quality
98 and retention of bioactive compounds in fruit powders (Swaminathan et al., 2015). High drying
99 temperatures can cause degradation of heat-sensitive compounds, such as anthocyanins, vitamin
100 C, and phenolics, leading to a loss of color, flavor, and antioxidant activity. On the other hand,
101 very low temperatures may prolong drying time, increase energy consumption, and result in
102 powders with poor physical characteristics, such as reduced flowability, solubility, and rehydration
103 capacity (Gamal et al., 2023). Understanding how different drying temperatures affect these
104 bioactive compounds helps in developing an optimized drying process that retains the maximum
105 nutritional and functional qualities of the product (Wojdyło et al., 2020).

106 The present study focused on evaluating the effect of different drying temperatures on the
107 physicochemical characteristics, colour attributes, and bioactive compound retention of *Syzygium*

108 *cumini* pulp powder. The outcomes of this study provide promising insights for the development
109 of bioactive-enriched *Syzygium cumini* (jamun) powder standardized by its improved shelf
110 stability, superior sensory attributes, and enhanced nutritional quality. The optimized drying
111 process not only aids in the preservation of heat-sensitive phytochemicals such as anthocyanins,
112 phenolics, and vitamin C but also ensures desirable physicochemical properties, including colour,
113 solubility, and flowability. Consequently, the resultant jamun powder holds significant potential
114 as a functional ingredient in the formulation of value-added food products, beverages,
115 nutraceuticals, and dietary supplements aimed at promoting health and wellness.

116 2. Materials and methods

117 2.1 Raw Material

118 Jamun fruits were procured from the Local market of Solan (Himachal Pradesh) and
119 Chandigarh in the month of July-August, 2022, while wild jamun fruits (var- Ra- jamun) were
120 procured from district Bilaspur (HP) from an altitude of 1800 m in the month of June-July,
121 2022.

122 2.2 Optimization of conditions for the preparation of jamun powder

123 The experiment was conducted to optimize the drying parameters for Jamun pulp to achieve
124 maximum drying efficiency and anthocyanin retention. The goal was to develop a scientifically
125 standardized process for producing high-quality, nutrient-rich Jamun powder. Pulp was prepared
126 and passed through a pulper for the extraction of pulp. The extracted pulp was homogenized,
127 heated, and filled in pre-sterilized glass bottles, followed by processing at $90\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 25 minutes.
128 The pulp was then used for standardizing the conditions of powder preparation by drying it in a
129 mechanical dehydrator at different temperatures (45 °C, 50 °C, 55 °C, and 60 °C), which was
130 subsequently pulverized into a fine powder. The conditions were optimized on the criteria of
131 drying yield and total anthocyanin content.

132 2.2.1 Powder Yield (%)

133 Yield of fruit powder was estimated by dividing the dried material by the fresh weight of fruit
134 expressed in terms of per cent with the formula given below:

$$135 \text{Yield (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of dried material}}{\text{Fresh weight of fruit}}$$

136

137 2.2.2 Flow properties of powder

138 The powder flow properties, or flowability, determine the powders potential to flow in a desired
139 manner in a specific instrument or equipment. The flowability is affected by various factors,
140 including particle size, surface texture, moisture content, and sugar content. The fruit powders
141 were evaluated for their flow properties by determining their bulk Density, tapped Density, Carr
142 index, Hausner ratio, and angle of repose, following standard procedures (Suhag et al., 2024).

143 2.2.3 Bulk Density and Tapped Density

144 The bulk density and tapped density of Jamun pulp powder were determined using a modified
145 method described by (Sarabandi et al., 2018). To measure bulk density, 20 g of the powder sample
146 was carefully transferred into a 50 mL graduated cylinder. The cylinder was handled gently to
147 avoid compaction, and the initial volume occupied by the powder was recorded. Bulk density was
148 then calculated as the ratio of the powders mass to this measured volume. For tapped density, the
149 same cylinder containing the sample was tapped 100 times on a laboratory bench from a height of
150 approximately 10 cm. This tapping allowed the particles to settle more closely together, reducing

151 the powder volume. The tapped density was calculated by dividing the mass of the powder by the
 152 reduced volume after tapping. These measurements help in understanding the flow characteristics,
 153 packing behavior, and handling properties of the Jamun pulp powder, which are essential for
 154 processing, packaging, and product formulation.

155

$$156 \quad \text{Bulk Density} = \frac{\text{Mass of powder}}{\text{Bulk Volume}}$$

157 Where, Mass of powder = W (in grams); Bulk volume = Vb (in mL or cm³)

158

159 **Tapped density**

160 Tapped density refers to the mass of the powder divided by the volume after tapping (usually
 161 after 100, 500, or 1250 taps).

$$162 \quad \text{Tapped Density} = \frac{\text{Tapped Volume}}{\text{Mass of powder}}$$

163 Where, Mass of powder = W; Tapped volume = Vt

164

165 **2.2.4 Hausner ratio and Carr compressibility**

166 Carr Index and Hausner Ratio were calculated from bulk and tapped Density, which determines
 167 the flowability and Compressibility of powders. The scale of flowability according to the US
 168 Pharmacopeia is given in **Table 1**. The following formula was used:

169

$$170 \quad \text{Hausner Ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density (TD)}}{\text{Bulk Density (BD)}}$$

$$171 \quad \text{Carr's Index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk Density}}{\text{Tapped Density}} \times 100$$

172

173 **Table 1. Classification Scale for Powder Flowability**

Carrs Compressibility (%)	Flow Behaviour	Hausner Ratio
Up to 10%	Exceptional flow	1.00–1.11
11–15%	Good flow properties	1.12–1.18
16–20%	Moderate / Fair flow	1.19–1.25
21–25%	Adequate / Passable	1.26–1.34
26–31%	Poor flowability	1.35–1.45
32–37%	Very poor flow	1.46–1.59

Above 38%	Extremely poor flow	>1.60
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176 2.2.5 Colour measurement

177 The colour characteristics of the samples were evaluated using a Lovibond Colour Tintometer
 178 (Model PFX-I Series spectrophotometer). This instrument provided colour readings in both RYBN
 179 units and the standard CIE (Commission Internationale de l'Éclairage) colour space parameters,
 180 namely L^* , a^* , and b^* . The L^* value indicates the lightness of the sample on a scale of 0 to 100,
 181 where 100 represents pure white and 0 represents pure black. The a^* coordinate reflects the colour
 182 transition from green (negative values) to red (positive values), while the b^* coordinate represents
 183 the shift from blue (negative values) to yellow (positive values). Each sample was analysed in
 184 triplicate following the procedure outlined in (Adit et al., 2024) to ensure accuracy and
 185 reproducibility. In addition, chroma (C^*) and hue angle (h°), which describe colour intensity and
 186 the overall colour tone, respectively, were calculated using the formulas provided by (IAOAC,
 187 2012). These parameters help in understanding the visual quality and consistency of the Jamun
 188 pulp powder.

189

$$190 \quad h^\circ = \tan^{-1} \frac{b^*}{a^*}$$

191

$$192 \quad C = \sqrt{(a^*)^2 + (b^*)^2}$$

192

193 Where L^* (darkness-lightness), a^* (red–green), and b^* (yellow–blue) are parameters of colour
 194 measurement.

195 2.2.6 Moisture content (%)

196 Moisture content was determined using a KI 250 (b) moisture analyzer based on the loss-on-drying
 197 principle. In this procedure, the instrument first records the initial weight of the sample, then heats
 198 it under controlled conditions to remove moisture. Once the sample is fully dried, the analyzer
 199 automatically measures the final weight. The difference between the initial and final weights
 200 represents the amount of moisture lost, allowing the moisture content to be accurately calculated.

201 2.2.7 Water activity (a_w)

202 A computer digital water activity meter (Rotronic Hygropalm) was used to measure the water
 203 activity (a_w) of the sample at room temperature. The sample was filled in a standard cuvette up to
 204 the rim and placed below the water activity meter sensor, which gives a direct reading of the
 205 sample's water activity according to (IAOAC, 2012).

206 2.2.8 pH

207 pH is defined as the negative logarithm of the molar concentration of hydrogen ions; it is the free
 208 hydrogen ion activity. The pH meter (ELTOP-3030 pH meter) was calibrated with buffer solutions
 209 of 4.0, 7.0, and 9.0. The pH of fruit pulp was taken directly with the pH meter according to
 210 (IAOAC, 2012). For powders and tablets, the pH was taken by reconstituting the sample. 1g
 211 sample was mixed using a magnetic stirrer in 10 ml of distilled water, and was kept for 1 hour
 212 before taking the reading in the pH meter.

213 2.3 Total soluble solids (TSS)

214 The total soluble solids of the fruit powder sample were prepared by mixing 1 g of the sample in
 215 10 mL of distilled water and letting it stand for 1 hour. The total soluble solids were measured

216 using a hand refractometer (Model ERMA) of 0-32°B, 28-62°B and 58-92°B ranges. Three
217 replications were taken for each sample, and the mean value was reported.

218 **2.4 Titratable acidity (%)**

219 Titratable acidity was determined by titrating a known volume of the sample against a standard
220 solution of NaOH, using phenolphthalein as an indicator. For powder and tablet, the samples were
221 prepared by weighing a known amount of sample and making up the volume with distilled water
222 before using the filtrate to determine the titratable acidity. The titratable acidity was expressed as
223 a percentage according to IAOAC, 2012 as per the given formula:

$$224$$

$$225 \text{ Titratable acidity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Normality of alkali} \times \text{Volume made up} \times \text{Eq. weight of dominant acid} \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample} \times \text{Volume of aliquot} \times 1000}$$

$$226$$

227

228 **2.5 Antioxidant activity (%)**

229 Antioxidant activity (free radical scavenging) was measured, where 3.9 mL of 6×10^{-5} mol/L
230 DPPH (2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) was used as a source of the free radical, was put into a
231 cuvette with 0.1 mg of powder (sample extracted in methanol), and the absorbance was measured
232 at 515 nm after 30 minutes, and methanol was used as a blank (Ranganna, 2009). Antioxidant
233 activity was calculated using the following equation:

$$234$$

$$235 \text{ Antioxidant activity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Ab(B)} - \text{Ab(S)}}{\text{Ab(B)}} \times 1002$$

236 Where, Ab (B) = Absorbance of blank Ab (S) = Absorbance of sample

237

238 **2.6 Total ash (%)**

239 Total ash content was determined using a standard gravimetric procedure. A known quantity of
240 the sample was placed into pre-weighed silica crucibles. The oven-dried samples (previously used
241 for moisture determination) were first heated gently on a hot plate until most of the organic matter
242 was charred and visible fumes were no longer produced. Following this initial carbonization, the
243 crucibles were transferred to a muffle furnace and ashed at 550°C for 5 hours, ensuring complete
244 oxidation of the remaining organic matter. The process continued until a clean, carbon-free white
245 ash with a constant weight was obtained. The ash content was calculated based on the weight of
246 the residue and expressed as a percentage on a fresh weight basis according to the method
247 described in (Nagendra et al., 2023), as shown below.

$$248$$

$$249 \text{ Ash (\%)} = \frac{\text{Weight of ash}}{\text{Weight of the sample taken}} \times 100$$

250 **2.7 Total phenols (mg/100g)**

251 The total phenolic content of the samples was estimated using the Folin–Ciocalteu colorimetric
252 method, with catechol serving as the standard phenolic compound. Approximately 1 mg of the
253 sample was placed in a clean mortar and homogenized with 1 mL of methanol to ensure efficient
254 extraction of phenolic compounds. The mixture was then centrifuged using a Revolutionary

255 Research Centrifuge for 20 minutes at 5000 rpm to obtain a clear supernatant. From the resulting
256 extract, 1 mL of an aliquot was transferred into a test tube, followed by the addition of 5 mL of
257 10% Folin–Ciocalteu reagent. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand for 10 minutes, 4 mL
258 of 7% sodium carbonate solution was added to develop the characteristic blue coloration. The
259 tubes were then incubated in a water bath maintained at 30–40°C for 40 minutes to facilitate
260 complete colour development, after which they were cooled to room temperature. The absorbance
261 of the samples was measured at 765 nm using a UV–VIS spectrophotometer (Model Shimadzu,
262 Japan). Phenolic concentration was calculated based on the standard calibration curve prepared
263 from catechol solutions ranging between 8 and 32 µg/mL. These measurements help in assessing
264 the antioxidant potential and bioactive quality of the Jamun pulp powder, as phenolic compounds
265 play a key role in imparting health benefits and stability to the product.

266 **2.8 Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)**

267 The ascorbic acid content was estimated using the AOAC method with 2,6-dichlorophenol
268 indophenol dye. The sample was extracted in 3 percent meta-phosphoric acid and was titrated with
269 dye to the pink color endpoint (Ranganna, 2009). The results were expressed as mg per 100 g of
270 sample and calculated by using the formula given below:

$$271 \quad \text{Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times \text{Dye factor} \times \text{Volume made up}}{\text{Aliquot of extract taken} \times \text{Weight of sample taken}} \times 100$$

272

273 **2.9 Anthocyanins**

274 Total anthocyanins present in all samples were determined by the spectrophotometric method
275 given by (Ranganna, 2009). The procedure involves the extraction of anthocyanins with 8%
276 ethanolic HCl and measuring their optical Density at 535 nm in a UV-Vis spectrophotometer
277 (Model UV-1650 P,C Shimadzu, Japan).

278 **2.10 Equilibrium relative humidity (%)**

279 The equilibrium relative humidity (ERH) of the powder samples was determined using the
280 standard static gravimetric method. Approximately 5 g of the sample was evenly spread on pre-
281 weighed petri dishes and placed inside desiccators containing sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) solutions of
282 different concentrations. These solutions generated a wide range of controlled relative humidity
283 conditions, covering 0–100% RH. The samples were allowed to equilibrate for 24-hour intervals,
284 during which the gain or loss in weight was recorded. This process was continued until each sample
285 reached a constant weight, indicating moisture equilibrium with the surrounding environment.
286 Once equilibrium was achieved, the moisture equilibrium data were plotted against the respective
287 relative humidity levels to determine the ERH of the samples, following the procedures described
288 in (Ranganna, 2009; Nagendra et al., 2023). The ERH experiments were carried out at ambient
289 laboratory temperatures (18.5–31.5°C). To assess the stability and moisture sensitivity of the
290 product, the critical and danger points for each sample were evaluated using the weight equilibrium
291 method outlined by (Jiang et al., 2025; Wink et al., 1946). These parameters provide valuable
292 insights into the storage behaviour, shelf life, and moisture-related quality changes in the Jamun
293 pulp powder.

294 **2.11 Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy**

295 FTIR analysis of the samples was performed using the potassium bromide (KBr) pellet method,
296 following standard procedures. Approximately 2 mg of the finely dried sample was thoroughly
297 mixed with spectroscopic-grade KBr and compressed into a transparent pellet suitable for infrared
298 measurement. The spectra were obtained using a Perkin Elmer Spectrum 400 FT-IR/FIR

299 Spectrometer (USA), ensuring high accuracy and sensitivity. The infrared spectra were recorded
300 over the 4000–450 cm^{-1} wavenumber range with a resolution of 0.4 cm^{-1} , allowing for precise
301 identification of functional groups. The characteristic absorption bands observed in the spectra
302 were interpreted according to the guidelines and classifications described in (Stuart et al., 2005).
303 This analysis helped in identifying the major functional groups present in the Jamun pulp powder,
304 offering insights into its structural, biochemical, and compositional characteristics.

305 **2.122 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis**

306 The particle size and morphology of jamun powder were analyzed using a digital Scanning
307 Electron Microscope (SEM – JSM 6100 (JEOL)) equipped with a digital image processor
308 instrument. Analysis was performed at the magnification range of 150X to 1000X and an
309 accelerating voltage of 15 KV.

310

311 **3. Result and Discussion**

312 Jamun fruits have a high titre of vitamins and bioactive compounds like anthocyanins along with
313 an appreciable amount of moisture content, thereby, to increase the shelf life and easy handling
314 process, the fruit is converted into powders. Thus, the pulp procedure standardized was used for
315 the preparation of jamun powder by conducting drying studies at different temperatures i.e., 45,
316 50, 55, 60, and 65°C in a mechanical dehydrator.

317 **3.1 Dehydration characteristics of jamun powders**

318 The dehydration characteristics of jamun powder prepared from pulp extracted by the hot
319 extraction method with 0.2 percent citric acid presented in (**Figure 1**).

320 Dehydration characteristics of jamun pulp showed that, irrespective of the temperature of drying
321 in comparison to the total period of drying, the rate of dehydration was fast during the initial period
322 of drying. At 45°C temperature, about 50 percent (fwb) of the moisture was removed within the
323 first 5.0 hours of drying, thereafter, the rate of drying slowed down. It took about 13 hours to dry
324 the jamun pulp to a powder of about 8.25 per cent moisture content at 45°C drying temperature.
325 Earlier (Nan et al., 2018), also stated that the rate of moisture removed is slowest during the falling
326 rate period of drying than that of the constant rate period. Similarly, the drying characteristics
327 (fwb) at 50°C. Showed that 50 per cent of the moisture from the pulp was reduced in the first 4
328 hours, and thereafter the drying slowed down, which took an overall time period of 10 hours from
329 jamun pulp to dry to a moisture content of 8.03 per cent.

330

331 **Figure 1. Drying behavior of jamun pulp at different temperatures**

332 The dehydration characteristics of jamun pulp at 55°C showed that, during the total drying period,
 333 the rate of dehydration was fast during the initial 3 hours, during which 49.47% of the moisture
 334 was lost. Thereafter, the rate of drying slowed down, and it took 8.0 hours for the jamun pulp to
 335 reach a moisture content of 7.98%. At a 60°C drying temperature, it took approximately 7 hours
 336 to dry the jamun pulp to a powder with a moisture content of about 7.90%. Similarly, the drying
 337 characteristics (fwb) and moisture content of the pulp showed that at a 65°C temperature, 50
 338 percent moisture was reduced in the first 2.0 hours and took about 6 hours to reduce the moisture
 339 content to 7.35 percent.

340 Dehydration characteristics shows that with the similar tray load and moisture content, the
 341 dehydration time taken for drying of jamun pulp at 45°C temperature for 13 hours with a powder
 342 yield of 8.71 per cent and the dehydration ratio as 11.48 while at 50°C temperature the time take
 343 to dry the similar quantity of pulp was 10 hours with powder yield of 9.90 per cent with
 344 dehydration ratio of 10:10. At drying temperature 55°C, 60°C and 65°C, the drying time taken was
 345 8, 7 and 6 hours respectively with powder yield as 12.43, 10.91 and 10.54 percent respectively.
 346 On the basis of anthocyanin content, drying of jamun pulp at 55°C resulted in maximum
 347 anthocyanins as 998.32 mg/100g, as against 954.29 mg/100g at 65°C. The amount of anthocyanin
 348 content at drying temperatures of 45°C, 50°C, and 60°C was observed as 981.06, 989.39, and
 349 960.28 mg/100g. Exposure to higher drying temperatures (60 and 65°C) leads to decreased
 350 anthocyanin content, while temperatures like 45 and 50°C may also reduce the amount of total
 351 anthocyanins due to prolonged heat treatment, leading to the destruction of anthocyanin content
 352 during the drying process. Thus, on the basis of total anthocyanin content, the drying temperature
 353 of 55 °C is hereby optimized as shown in (Table 2).

354

355 **Table 2. Dehydration characteristics of jamun powders at different temperature conditions**

356

Temperature (°C)	Drying time (h)	Dehydration Ratio	Yield (%)	Moisture (%)	Total anthocyanin content (mg/100g)
45	13	11.48	8.71	8.25	981.06
50	10	10.10	9.90	8.03	989.39
55	8	8.04	12.43	7.98	998.32
60	7	9.16	10.91	7.90	960.28
65	6	9.48	10.54	7.35	954.29

357

358 3.2 Colour characteristics of jamun powder

359 Colour is an important quality attribute in the food industry, which influences the consumer
 360 preference and acceptability of the product. The data presented in (Table 3 and Figure 2) represent
 361 the colour values (L^* , a^* , b^*) of jamun powder at different temperatures, namely 45, 50, 55, 60,
 362 and 65 °C. The colour values of jamun powder were reported to be 42.82 for L^* , 18.37 for a^* , and
 363 41.43 for b^* at 45 °C drying temperature, 42.80 for L^* , 19.45 for a^* , and 43.45 for b^* at 50 °C,
 364 and 44.70 for L^* , 20.74 for b^* , 44.41 for a^* , at 55° C. The L^* , a^* , b^* values were recorded as
 365 40.30, 19.38, 45.42, respectively, at 60°C while 40.18, 19.03, 45.43, respectively at 65°C. The
 366 values were contrary to the values reported by (Shishir et al., 2014). The values a^* and b^* observed
 367 were in accordance with the values reported by (Wadia et al., 2020). However, the L^* values
 368 observed were higher.

369

370 **Table 3. Colour characteristics of jamun powder at different temperatures**

371

Properties	Temperature (°C)				
	45°C	50°C	55°C	60°C	65°C
L^* (Lightness)	42.82	42.80	44.70	40.30	40.18
a^* (Redness- Greenness)	18.37	19.45	20.74	19.38	19.03
b^* (Yellowness- Blueness)	41.43	43.45	44.41	45.42	45.43
ΔE	62.34	64.01	66.33	63.73	63.56

372

373 Thus, from the above results, it was concluded that drying of jamun pulp at 55°C temperature was
 374 standardized on the basis of a higher amount of total anthocyanin content (998.32 mg/100g) and
 375 colour value of the extracted powder. Thus, 55°C temperature for drying of jamun pulp was
 376 selected for further studies.

377
378

379 **Figure 2. CIE color model readings of jamun powder dried at 45, 50, 55, 60, 65. °C**

380

381 **3.3 Flow properties of jamun pulp powder**

382 The flow properties of jamun pulp powder dried at 55°C depicted the bulk Density and tapped
 383 Density as 0.66 ± 0.02 g/mL and 0.73 ± 0.03 g/mL, respectively (**Table 4**). The bulk Density of
 384 powder influences the arrangement of particles, and the powder with lower bulk Density will
 385 collapse easily when dispersed. The tapped Density of a powder is determined as the volume
 386 occupied after tapping, and it influences the powder's packing conditions (Caliskan et al., 2013;
 387 Akar et al., 2019). The water absorption index and water solubility index of jamun powder were
 388 2.88 ± 0.05 and 0.57 ± 0.03 , respectively. High water absorption capacity determines the hydrophilic
 389 nature and high hydrogen bonding of protein molecules (Bellissent-Funel et al., 2016), and the
 390 high value of water solubility index in the finer fraction may be due to an emulsion formed, which
 391 restricts the separation of particles adequately after centrifugation and leaching of water-soluble
 392 components (Xiao et al., 2025). The lower the bulk Density, the higher the porosity in jamun pulp

393 powder, as 13.81 ± 0.08 percent. The bulk Density and tapped Density influence the Carr index and
 394 Hausner ratio, which are in inverse relationship with the powder compressibility and flowability.
 395 The Carr index was determined as (good), with the Hausner ratio as 1.25 (Passable), according to
 396 the values calculated and the classification given by Jebitta et al. (2016). The jamun pulp powder
 397 was determined to be moderately passable.

398 The inter-particle force, such as Van der Waal forces and the moisture content of the powder,
 399 influences the cohesiveness of the powder, the higher the moisture content, the less flowable the
 400 powder (Li et al., 2004). The flowability is also due to the particle adhesion, which is influenced
 401 by the sugar content in the powders, since the sugar content is higher in jamun pulp powder, thus
 402 the flowability of the powder was reduced (Pombo et al., 2020). The powders were further used
 403 for the extraction of anthocyanins.

404

405 **Table 4. Different Flow properties of jamun powder**

406

Parameters	Mean \pm S.E*
Powder yield (%)	12.43 ± 0.22
Bulk Density (g/mL)	0.66 ± 0.02
Tapped Density (g/mL)	0.73 ± 0.03
Water absorption index (g/g)	2.88 ± 0.05
Water solubility index (g/g)	0.57 ± 0.03
Carr index (%)	Good
Porosity (%)	13.81 ± 0.08
Hausner ratio	1.25 (Passable)

407 **S.E*= Standard error**408 **3.4 Chemical characteristics of jamun powder**

409 The chemical characteristics of jamun powder (**Table 5**) revealed the moisture content and water
 410 activity as 7.98 ± 0.18 per cent and 0.36 ± 0.04 , respectively, which were similar to the values
 411 observed by (Luke et al., 2005). The TSS, pH, and titratable acidity of jamun powder were
 412 observed to be $67.40^\circ\text{B} \pm 0.08$, 3.70 ± 0.12 , and 9.53 ± 0.10 percent, respectively. The ascorbic
 413 acid, total phenols, and anthocyanin content were recorded as 18.43 ± 0.27 , 1025.83 ± 0.80 , and
 414 998.83 ± 0.72 mg/100g, respectively. The data reported were in accordance with the values given
 415 by Rao et al. (2011) and Verma et al. (2018) in guava powder.

416 The moisture content of the powder is reduced during drying, which is responsible for significant
 417 changes in the chemical characteristics of the fruit powders compared to the fresh fruit (Kucharska
 418 et al., 2025). Removal of moisture content concentrated the bioactive compounds manifold, thus
 419 resulting in an overall increase in the compounds. Further, the titratable acidity of the fruit powders
 420 increased during dehydration, as the drying temperatures increased the molecular vibrations, which
 421 prevent hydrogen bond formation, resulting in free H^+ ions contributing to the increased acidity
 422 (Moldovan et al., 2021). The increase in total phenols, anthocyanin content, and antioxidant
 423 activity during drying may be attributed to the release of bound phenolic acids at high
 424 temperatures, which have a positive correlation with radical scavenging activity (Babaei et al.,
 425 2025; Zhang et al., 2025). Decrease in ascorbic acid was probably due to its heat, light, and oxygen-
 426 sensitive nature as well as the dilution effect exerted by the addition of foaming agent (Yin et al.,
 427 2022). Moreover, the extracted jamun powder contained a significant amount of macro minerals,

428 including sulfur (6.90 ppm), phosphorus (8.89 ppm), copper (0.28 ppm), zinc (0.78 ppm), and iron
429 (14.09 ppm).

430

431 **Table 5. Various chemical characteristics of jamun powder**

432

Parameters	Mean \pm S.E*
Moisture (%)	7.98 \pm 0.18
Water activity (a_w)	0.36 \pm 0.04
TSS ($^{\circ}$ B)	67.40 \pm 0.08
pH	3.70 \pm 0.12
Titratable acidity (% citric acid)	9.53 \pm 0.10
Ascorbic acid (mg/100g)	18.43 \pm 0.27
Total phenols (mg/100g)	1025.83 \pm 0.80
Antioxidant activity (% DPPH)	86.79 \pm 0.02
Anthocyanins (mg/100g)	998.32 \pm 0.73
Minerals (ppm)	
Phosphorus	8.89
Sulphur	6.90
Copper	0.28
Zinc	0.78
Iron	14.09

433 S.E*= Standard error

434

435 **3.5 Equilibrium Relative Humidity (ERH) Study of Jamun Powder**

436 ERH data in jamun powder revealed that at 30.00 percent relative humidity, the powder had a
437 moisture content of 5.52 percent. Data presented in **Table 6** further indicates that the powder
438 exposed to 50.00 per cent relative humidity exhibited considerable changes in the colour and
439 texture within 11 days of exposure.

440

441 **Table 6. Measurement of the Equilibrium relative humidity (%) of jamun powder with time**

442

Relative humidity (%)	Equilibrium moisture content (%)	No. of days to reach equilibrium	Remarks
0	1.438	14	Normal colour and texture
10	3.541	13	Normal colour and texture
20	4.536	13	Normal colour and texture
30	5.525	13	Normal colour and texture
40	6.410	13	Normal colour and texture
50	7.464	11	Normal colour and texture
60	8.768	10	Dark colour and soft texture
70	9.531	9	Dark colour and soft texture
80	14.43	7	Dark colour and lump formation
90	19.77	7	Lump formation with an off odour

100	28.04	5	Mould growth with an off odour
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Thus, the critical point and danger point (5% lower relative humidity than the crucial point) for jamun powder were recorded at relative humidities of 50.00% and 45.00%, respectively. At 40.00 per cent relative humidity, there was no change in the powder colour and flowability, while there was darkening of the powder when stored at relative humidity beyond 50.00 per cent. The product exposed to 80.00% relative humidity exhibited considerable changes in colour and texture within 7 to 9 days of exposure. Thus, the critical point (characterized by dark color and lumps formation in the powder) and danger point (5% lower relative humidity than the critical point) for the powder were calculated at 55% relative humidity. When the product was stored at 100 percent relative humidity, mould growth appeared after 5 days of storage. Henceforth, different fractions of jamun powder fall in the category of hygroscopic substances. Thus, it is evident that jamun powder should be stored in a relative humidity of 55 percent. The relationship between equilibrium moisture content and the number of days required for the powders to reach equilibrium is presented in (figures 3 and 4).

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459
460

Figure 3. Humidity moisture equilibrium curve for jamun powder

461

Figure 4. Graphical interpolation isotherm for jamun powder

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463

464 The moisture-humidity relationship of the product indicated three key stability points

- 465 • Initial Point: At 45% relative humidity, the sample reached an equilibrium moisture content
- 466 of 5.98%.
- 467 • Danger Point: At 55% relative humidity, the equilibrium moisture content increased to
- 468 7.46%, indicating the onset of potential quality deterioration.
- 469 • Critical Point: At 60% relative humidity, the equilibrium moisture content rose further to
- 470 8.76%, marking the threshold beyond which the product becomes highly susceptible to
- 471 spoilage or structural changes.

472 The jamun powder was stored in glass vials for conducting the storage study, both under ambient
 473 and refrigerated conditions. There was a non-significant change in moisture content, phenols, and
 474 anthocyanin content during 6 months of storage. Thus, it was concluded that six months of storage
 475 of jamun powder under refrigerated conditions retained its maximum quality characteristics, and
 476 therefore, it was further used for anthocyanin extraction.

477

478 3.6 FTIR spectroscopy of jamun powder

479 Analysis of the fingerprint region of spectra revealed the presence of tri-substituted alkenes and
 480 anhydrides (Stuart, et al., 2005). An infrared spectrum of jamun powder is presented in the (**figure**
 481 **5**). Revealed the peaks, whereas their intensities indicated the presence of a significant amount of
 482 phytochemicals in jamun powder (**Table 7**). The FTIR analysis of jamun powder showed the
 483 presence of hydroxyl group of alkenes and aromatic groups which signifies the compound
 484 anthocyanin (cyanidin) in particular, with the absorption ranging from 2258 (N=C=O) Isocyanate

485 class, 2228-2191 (C=C) Alkyne class, 2094 (C-H) aromatic compound, 1938 (C=C=C) Aldehyde
 486 class and 1045 (CO-O-CO) anhydride, respectively. FTIR spectra show the presence of the
 487 cyanidin compound of anthocyanin in jamun powder dried at 55°C.
 488

489

490 **Figure 5. FTIR spectra of Jamun powder**

491

492 **Table 7. FTIR analysis of jamun powder**

493

Absorption (cm ⁻¹)	Appearance	Group	Compound class
2258	Strong, broad	N=C=O	Isocyanate
2228	Weak	C≡C stretching	Alkyne
2191	Weak	C≡C stretching	Alkyne
2094	Weak	C-H bending	Aromatic compound
1938	Medium	C=C=C	Allene
2853	Medium	C-H stretching	Aldehyde
1045	Strong, broad	CO-O-CO	Anhydride

494

495 3.7 SEM analysis of jamun powder

496 The external surface characteristics of the best treatment obtained at 55 °C were analyzed at
 497 different magnifications using SEM, depicted in (**Figure 6a-e**). The morphology of the surface
 498 revealed a smooth and shriveled appearance of the particles in the jamun powder dried at 55 °C,
 499 which could be attributed to the shrinkage of particles after moisture loss. The surface was quite
 500 uneven, with a large number of grooves; however, no hollow pores or agglomerates were observed,
 501 even at 1000x magnification. This indicates that the drying temperature was optimal and did not
 alter the surface morphology of the powder. The lack of hollow pores also validates the flow

502 characteristics of the powder. Similar interpretations of surface morphology were given by (Azian
 503 et al., 2004; An et al., 2016).

504

505

506 **Figure 6. SEM analysis of jamun powder at 55°C at different magnifications viz., (a) 150,**
 507 **(b) 350, (c) 550, (d) 800 and (e) 1000**

508

509 **Conclusion**

510 Mechanical drying of Jamun pulp at 55°C was identified as the optimal condition for producing
 511 high-quality Jamun powder. Drying at this temperature yielded superior results based on higher
 512 drying efficiency, as well as enhanced retention of total anthocyanins, total phenolics, ascorbic
 513 acid, and antioxidant activity. These optimized conditions ensured the production of premium-
 514 quality Jamun powder. The final characteristics of the powder were largely influenced by the
 515 drying process. By carefully controlling temperature and drying duration, it was possible to remove

516 moisture efficiently without compromising the nutritional integrity or sensory attributes of the
517 fruit. Key physicochemical properties, including bulk density, moisture content, particle size
518 distribution, and water activity, were thoroughly evaluated. The powder exhibited desirable
519 features such as high bulk density, low moisture content, and fine particle size, making it suitable
520 for incorporation into a wide range of food products. Furthermore, the powder demonstrated good
521 storage stability, with minimal changes in color, flavor, or nutrient composition over time. Overall,
522 the findings indicate that Jamun powder has strong potential as a functional and nutritious
523 ingredient for the food and nutraceutical industries. Future research may focus on exploring
524 alternative drying technologies, profiling the specific bioactive compounds responsible for its
525 health benefits, and assessing its applications in functional foods and nutraceutical formulations.

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530 **Author's Contribution**

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536 **Conflict of Interest**

537 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

538 **Data Availability Statement**

539 All data are available within this manuscript. There is no associated data.

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